

DEEP LEARNING FOR BIRD SPECIES RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

Now a day some bird species are being found rarely and if found classification of bird species prediction is difficult. Naturally, birds present in various scenarios appear in different sizes, shapes, colors, and angles from human perspective. Besides, the images present strong variations to identify the bird species more than audio classification. Also, human ability to recognize the birds through the images is more understandable. So this method uses the Caltech-UCSD Birds 200 [CUB-200-2011] dataset for training as well as testing purpose. By using deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) algorithm an image converted into grey scale format to generate autograph by using tensor flow, where the multiple nodes of comparison are generated. These different nodes are compared with the testing dataset and score sheet is obtained from it. After analyzing the score sheet it can predicate the required bird species by using highest score.

1. INTRODUCTION

BIRD behavior and population trends have become an important issue now a days. Birds help us to detect other organisms in the environment (e.g. insects they feed on) easily as they respond quickly to the environmental changes [2]. But, gathering and collecting information about birds requires huge human effort as well as becomes a very costlier method. In such case, a reliable system that will provide large scale processing of information about birds

and will serve as a valuable tool for researchers, governmental agencies, etc. is required. So, bird species identification plays an important role in identifying that a particular image of bird belongs to which species. Bird species identification means predicting the bird species belongs to which category by using an image. But, due to the mixed sounds in environment such as insects, objects from real world, etc. processing of such information becomes more complicated. Bird species identification is a challenging task to humans as well as to computational.

The bird identification can be performed through images, audio, and video. By collecting the acoustic signal of birds, an audio processing technique allows for identification. However, processing such information becomes more difficult as a result of mixed sounds in the surroundings, such as insects, real-world items, and so on. Humans prefer visuals to music or video in most cases. Bird species identification is a difficult undertaking for both humans and computing methods that perform such tasks automatically [2].

As image-based classification systems are improving the task of classifying, objects are moving into datasets with far more categories such as Caltech-UCSD. Recent work has seen much success in this area. Caltech UCSD Birds 200(CUB-200-2011) is a wellknown dataset for bird images with photos of 200 categories.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Bird Species Identification using Deep Learning

Today, many species of birds are rarely found, and it is difficult to classify bird species when found. For example, for different scenarios, birds come with different sizes, forms, colors and from a human viewpoint with different angles. Indeed, the images show different differences that need to be recorded as audio recognition of bird species. It is also easier for people to identify birds in the pictures. Today, using deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) on GoogLe Net framework bird species classification is possible. For this experiment, a bird image was converted into a gray scale format that generated the autograph. After examining each and every autograph that calculates the score sheet from each node and predicts the respective bird species after the score sheet analysis. In this experiment, the Caltech-UCSD Birds 200 [CUB-200-2011] data collection was used for both training and testing purposes. For training purpose 500 labeled data are used and 200 unlabeled data are used for testing. For classification, Deep Convolutional Neural Networks are used and parallel processing was carried out using GPU technology. Final results show that the DCNN algorithm can be predicted at 88.33% of bird species. The experimental research is performed on the linux operating systems with Tensor flow library and using a NVIDIA Geforce GTX 680 with 2 GB RAM.

Bird Species Recognition Using Support Vector Machines

Automatic identification of bird species by their vocalization is studied in this paper. Bird sounds are represented with two different parametric representations: (i) the mel-cepstrum parameters and (ii) a set of low-level signal parameters, both of which have been found useful for bird species recognition. Recognition is performed in a

decision tree with support vector machine (SVM) classifiers at each node that perform classification between two species. Recognition is tested with two sets of bird species whose recognition has been previously tested with alternative methods. Recognition results with the proposed method suggest better or equal performance when compared to existing reference methods.

Identifying birds is one of challenging role for bird watchers due to the similarity of the birds' forms/image background and the lack of experience for watchers. So, it needs a computer system based images to help birdwatchers in order to identify birds. This study aims at investigating the use of deep learning for birds' identification using convolutional neural network for extracting features from images. The investigation was performed on database contained 4340 images that collected by the paper author from Jordan. The Principal Component Analysis (was applied on layer 6 and 7, as well as on the statistical operations of merging the two layers like: average, minimum, maximum and combine of both layers. The datasets were investigated by the following classifiers: Artificial neural networks, K-Nearest Neighbor, Random Forest, Naïve Bayes and Decision Tree. Whereas, the metrics used in each classifier are: accuracy, precision, recall, and F-Measure. The results of investigation include and not limited to the following, the PCA used on the deep features does not only reduce the dimensionality, and therefore, the training/testing time is reduced significantly, but also allows for increasing the identification accuracy, particularly when using the Artificial Neural Networks classifier. Based on the results of classifiers; Artificial neural networks showed high classification accuracy (70.9908), precision (0.718), recall (0.71) and F-Measure (0.708) compared to other classifiers.

3. SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

Existing System :-

In this paper, instead of recognizing a large number of disparate categories, the problem of recognizing a large number of classes within one category is investigated that of birds. Classifying birds pose an extra challenge over categories, because of the large similarity between classes. In addition, birds are non-rigid objects that can deform in many ways, and consequently there is also a large variation within classes. Previous work on bird classification has deal with a small number of classes, or through voice.

To implement this technique we need to train all birds species and generate a model and then by uploading any image deep learning algorithm will convert uploaded image into gray scale format and apply that image on train model to predict best match species name for uploaded image.

Proposed System :-

Represents the actual flow of the proposed system. To develop such system a trained dataset is required to classify an image. Trained dataset consists of two parts trained result and test result. The dataset has to be retrained to achieve higher accuracy in identification using retrain.py in Google Collab. The training dataset is made using 50000 steps taking into consideration that higher the number of steps higher is its accuracy. The accuracy of training dataset is 93%. The testing dataset consists of nearly 1000 images with an accuracy of 80%. dataset is validated with an accuracy of 75% to increase the performance of system. Whenever a user will upload an input file on website, the image is temporarily stored in database. This input file is then feed to system and given to CNN where CNN is coupled with trained dataset. A CNN consists of various convolutional layers. Various alignments/features such as head, body, color, beak, shape, entire image of bird are considered

for classification to yield maximum accuracy

Advantages :-

- dataset is validated with an accuracy of 75% to increase the performance of system.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter mainly provides the overview on modules of the application, objectives of the project and a detailed project overview.

Modules of the Application:

- To implement this technique we need to train all birds species and generate a model and then by uploading any image deep learning algorithm will convert uploaded image into gray scale format and apply that image on train model to predict best match species name for uploaded image.
- To train bird species we are using ‘Caltech-UCSD Birds 200(CUB-200-2011)’ dataset which contains 200 species or categories of birds. Model will be built using that dataset and tensor flow deep learning algorithm.

5. SCREEN SHOTS

User Login Screen:

To test this application i am using below images

In above screen some bird's images are there but we don't know its name or species name. So by uploading this image to application we can get their species name

To run this project double click on 'run.bat' file to get below screen

In above screen click on 'Upload Bird Image' button to upload bird image

In above screen i am uploading one image of bird called '457.jpg'. After upload will get below screen

Now click on 'Run DCNN Algorithm & View Identified Species' button to know the species name of uploaded bird

In above screen we got 5 related birds images of uploaded image and we can see the species name of bird on title bar of image. So by uploading any image we can know the name of bird. You can upload any image and get its name and uploading image name should be as integer value.

Now click on 'View Score Graph' button to view the graph

In above graph we got matching score of all 5 related birds and in above graph x-axis represents name of bird and y-axis represents matching score.

Accuracy value of this algorithm you can see in below screen

